

MATHEMATICAL SCIENCES

A MOVING WINDOW APPROACH TO IDENTIFICATION OF PATTERNS IN MULTIVARIATE TIME SERIES: APPLICATION TO THE MULTIVARIATE FAULT DETECTION OF ELECTRICAL SUBMERSIBLE PUMPS

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Abstract

The paper describes a multivariate time series pattern recognition method based on reference windows and used for the detection of fault patterns of electric submersible pumps caused by scales formed during production process in petroleum wells. Through a “moving window” strategy, the algorithm finds and selects reference windows in a long time series and computes the similarity between each selected window and the reference one (smaller time series) using the Euclidean distance. This method can simultaneously get the results of fault detection and fault diagnosis in a monitoring process. Results of algorithm analysis and fault detection experiments indicate the validity and practicability of the presented method.

Keywords: Multivariate time series, pattern recognition, reference window, electrical submersible pump.

1 Introduction

Subsea electric submersible pump (subsea ESP) is a lift method that has become common especially in low API oil production. Since 2015, this method has been successfully applied in mature oilfields of the Northeastern Offshore Region by PEMEX, Mexican Oil Company. Unfortunately, ESP are subject to changing downhole conditions, which lead to failures. Laboratory analysis of the damaged equipment made it possible to identify different types of faults. Although a large amount of operational data has been collected during the usage period, it is still a challenge to extract useful information to detect that the device has stopped working properly. The ability to predict common ESP failures before they occur with automatic pattern recognition, could considerably minimize well's downtime, and increase lifetime of the pumps.

On the experimental platform, typical failure conditions can be simulated for wax deposition, sand sticking, liquid filling dissatisfaction or valve leakage among others. Their working condition data are recorded and used to identify typical failure patterns [4]. Nevertheless, mineral deposits over the pump and motor body called scale or inlay, which are one the major causes of decrease of the pump efficiency and failures, are difficult to simulate in laboratory conditions, since the process depend on operational conditions different from well to well and can take several weeks or months. Thus, the development of data analysis methods based on collected operational data is a time challenge. Several proposals to develop a real-time diagnostic and preventive maintenance methods has been published recently in the literature [15], nevertheless, to our knowledge no such system has been implemented and tested so far.

Failure analysis based on recognition of behavior patterns of pump parameters corresponds to analysis of multivariate time series (MTS). In this paper, a pattern recognition method for MTS analysis is developed to identify inlays in ESP equipment. The method uses reference windows to extract patterns of typical conditions

leading to a pump's failure. Both numerical and categorical descriptions of the level and trend characteristic variables are used to cluster TS segments according to the presented typical patterns. Experimental results on different classifiers including kNN, Naïve Bayes, Random Forest, and n-layers ANN, are compared, giving the best classification accuracy of 97% on experimental real-life dataset for five wells with the kNN classifier.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. In the next section, theoretical background and related work are described. In Section 3, the proposed methodology is presented. Section 4 includes the discussion of the experimental results followed by conclusions.

2 Theoretical background and related work

2.1 Model-based fault diagnosis of Electric Submersible Pumps

ESP system consists of controller and transformers, which are surface components housed in an oil platform, as well as pump and motor, which are sub-surface components located in well hole. The pump itself is a multi-stage unit with number of stages being determined by the operating requirements. ESP failure can be electric, mechanical, thermal or fluid/gas composition, with a number of potential reasons, which can lead to them.

Fault Detection and Diagnosis (FDD) methods are divided into model-based (considering empirical models identified through historical data) and historical data-based [6]. Conventional most widely used model-based diagnosis methods are:

- Current cards.
- Vibration detection and analysis, motor current signature analysis (MCSA).
- Holding pressure diagnosis.
- Failure Mode, Effects and Criticality Analysis (FMECA) and Fault Tree Analysis (FTA) information.

Among these methods, current cards method is still the main one for ESP fault diagnosis in oil companies enabling extraction of features from current cards in different fault modes of ESP to recognize the faults

[19]. Nevertheless, this method has a low efficiency and is subject of inevitable human errors. Recently, few authors claimed vibration analysis, which refers to the study of the vibration signal obtained from the simulation test bench for different fault types, to be the most reliable way to monitor pump's state during fault simulation [21, 14]. For ESP, this method has limited applicability because various events such as tubing leakage or strong mechanical vibration may occur, and faults cannot be accurately diagnosed based on these parameters. Therefore, the operating parameters should be taken into account.

Zhang (2008) reported on the qualitative and quantitative analysis of ESP faults, based on the FTA method, where the fault tree of the ESP was developed. The minimum cut sets, minimum path sets, and structure function were also solved [20]. For more details on advanced model-based diagnosis methods see [10].

2.2 Data-driven Fault Detection and Diagnosis

Data-driven methods have been applied to different types of pumps' fault diagnostics, but only recently some applications to ESP have been reported due to the considerable differences in operational environments.

For example, back propagation algorithm, adaptive resonance network, and multiple mutation adaptive genetic algorithm-radial basis function neural network (MMAGA-RBFNN) for fault detection of a centrifugal pump were reported in [16]. The main problem of the proposed method is that it required a substantial data set difficult to obtain in practice for ESP: about 60 groups of labeled data from wax deposition, sand sticking, effect of gases, liquid filling dissatisfaction, valve leakage, and empty pumping were used as training samples. Provided experiments confirmed that more than one thousand samples were necessary to guarantee error rates of about 4%. Another approach to centrifugal pumps fault diagnosis have been reported by V. Muralidharan and V. Sugumaran (2014), who applied feature extraction using wavelets and classification using SVM [14]. The main advantage of the extraction of wavelet features and SVM classifiers compared to Bayes and J48 algorithms is that the latter require a lot of domain expertise and computational time. Fansen Konga and Ruheng Chen (2004) proposed a new combined diagnostic system for triplex pump based on wavelet transform, fuzzy logic and neural network [7]. Wavelet transform coefficients of non-faulty signals were used as network inputs to detect anomalies of faulty signals [17]. In all the above papers, researchers have reported on high classification accuracy.

In case of the ESP, statistical analysis techniques have still been widely used [11]. Nowadays, machine learning and data-driven models in predictive maintenance of ESP have been developed within a "digital oil-field" scenario [2, 7]. Most of recent research has either used only PCA as an unsupervised learning method for real-time diagnosis of ESP or applied surveillance-by-exception (detecting disruptive events). The trained classification algorithm is applied to the test data to detect points outside the confidence interval of the prediction [4, 8, 17]. Nevertheless, none of these has been a predictive approach. The predictive model has been developed in [1], where the PCA method was combined

with extreme gradient boosted trees machine learning technique. The authors report the accurate prediction of downhole failures seven days ahead, before the workover.

Intake pressure and temperature, discharge pressure, vibrations, motor, and system current and frequency measured at regular time intervals are most used as inputs to train the algorithms. Pumping process monitoring signals represent time series.

2.3 Multivariate TS analysis

Many time series encountered in practice are best viewed as components of a vector-valued (multivariate) time series $\{X_t\}$, which has a serial dependence within each component series $\{X_t\}$ and $\{X_t\}, i \neq j$. In the analysis of multivariate time series (MTS), the behavior of a second-order multivariate time series can be studied using the autocovariance matrices in the time domain, or the Fourier spectral density matrix in the frequency domain.

To specify the second-order properties, the covariance is a measure of dependence, not only between observations in the same series but also between the observations in different series:

$$\gamma_{ij}(t+h, t) = E[(X_{t+h,i} - \mu_{ti})(X_{tj} - \mu_{tj})] \quad (1)$$

Thus, an MTS vector will be defined by covariance matrices:

$$\Gamma(t+h, t) = \begin{bmatrix} \gamma_{11}(t+h, t) & \dots & \gamma_{1m}(t+h, t) \\ \gamma_{m1}(t+h, t) & \dots & \gamma_{mm}(t+h, t) \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

The series $\{X_t\}$ has a spectral representation:

$$X_t = \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} e^{i\lambda t} dZ(\lambda), \quad (3)$$

Where $\{Z(\lambda), -\pi < \lambda < \pi\}$ is a process, whose components are complex-valued processes.

Nonstationary univariate time series can frequently be made stationary by applying the differencing operator $\nabla = 1 - B$ repeatedly. The notion of cointegration captures the idea of univariate nonstationary time series "moving together".

2.4 TS similarity and clustering

An overview of time series clustering can be found in Liao (2005), although significant new contributions have been made since then [10]. They include such problems as time series representation, indexing and segmentation, dissimilarity measures, clustering techniques, and visualization tools. A crucial issue in cluster analysis is the similarity of data objects, i.e., determining an appropriate measure to be used. In TS, the concept of dissimilarity is particularly complex because values are interdependent, and dissimilarity must satisfy the properties of invariance to specific biases in the data.

In general, TS similarity measures can be divided into complexity-based, model-based, feature-based, and the prediction-based dissimilarity measures. If the goal is to compare profiles of series, conventional distances between raw data (such as the Minkowski distance typically used for orders 2 - Euclidean or 1 - Manhattan distance) that evaluate a one-to-one mapping of each pair of sequences can provide satisfactory results. Dynamic Time Warping (DTW) can be used in the presence of signal transformations such as shifting and/or scaling but ignores the TS behavior around the

points. To avoid this drawback, dissimilarity is measured by comparing sequences of serial features extracted from the original time series. Such features include autocorrelations, cross-correlations, spectral features, wavelet coefficients (DWT), and so on. Feature-based approaches aim to represent the dynamical structure of each series by a feature vector with lower dimension, which allows dimensionality reduction and significant computational time saving.

The symbolic aggregate approximation (SAX) representation approach introduced by Lin, Keogh, Lonardi, and Chiu (2003) first converts the original data into the piecewise aggregate approximation (PAA) representation and then symbolizes the PAA representation into a discrete string [13]. As a result, the SAX representation is very competitive to handle a variety of data mining problems, including cluster analysis of time series. However, extensive TS preprocessing (normalization - to obtain zero mean and unit variance, segmentation - segments of equal length, symbolic representation) is required.

3 Proposed methodology

3.1 Process variables

In the following, the case of faults caused by inlays (of sulfates and carbonates) is considered, which is one of the most typical types of failure (in the presence of sulfates) and difficult to diagnose. The previous analysis has identified seven wells with incrustations of the 60 wells in total with ESP. The following parameters are measured:

1. Pump Inlet Pressure (PIP)
2. Pump Discharge Pressure (PDP)
3. Pump inlet temperature (TIP)
4. Motor temperature (TM)
5. Leakage current (CLA)
6. Vibration measured in the BEC equipment (VIB)

7. Output frequency of the frequency converter (FRE)
8. Phase currents a,b,c measured at the output of the frequency converter (IA, IB, IC)
9. Output voltage of the frequency inverter (VOUT)
10. Pressure in the production piping (PTP)
11. Downstream pressure (PB)
12. Downstream temperature (TB)
13. Pressure in the casing (PTR)

In addition, the water properties used to identify possible sulfate scales are considered:

14. Percentage of water produced
15. Water salinity

3.2 Conditions of the failures caused by an inlay

According to historical data and fault analysis performed by PEMEX and IMP experts, the start of the fault period can be determined with the start of the current increase. At the same time, the motor temperatures are increasing and decreasing (**Fig. 1b**). Pressure of the production pipe (PTP) at the end of the pre-fault period drops drastically (**Fig. 1a**), while the pump inlet pressure (PIP) experiences a drastic rise (not seen in **Fig. 1** because of the difference in scales). The time horizon of an inlay operation can be determined to be about two months (dashed window), based on the time when the pressure begins to increase. The end of the window cannot be determined by the time of the fault itself. It is worth mentioning that the peaks observed in **Fig. 1** correspond to operating outputs and do not characterize the failure process (should be eliminated).

3.3 Fault classification method

The main idea of the proposed method is to represent the reference window (**Fig. 1**) as a sequence of smaller segments and corresponding clusters. The algorithm of the proposed methodology is presented in **Fig. 2**.

Fig. 1. The behavior of the characteristic variables of the ESP equipment a) pressure, b) temperature and reference window that correspond to an incrustation fault.

The pre-processing step includes elimination of peaks corresponding to operational outputs, correlation analysis and elimination of correlated variables and standardization of the series. What we are interested in are the trends, shapes and patterns existing in the data.

To recognize these patterns first it is required to discover the simple local trends such as “increase in the temperature” and “decrease in the pressure”. The algorithm is implemented as follows:

Fig. 2. Flow chart of the proposed methodology.

Fig. 3. A time series is discretized by first obtaining mean levels and trends for each segment a) and then b) using SAX.

1. Multivariate time series is first divided into a sequence of equal-sized segments by sliding a window incrementally across the time series, thus generating a set of reference time series (RTS). For each segment, linear regression is applied to obtain the trend. A mean value w_i is computed for each segment I obtaining a vector $W = \{w_1, \dots, w_s\}$ for each TS (Fig. 3a):

$$w_i = \frac{s}{m} \sum_{j=\frac{m}{s}(i-1)+1}^{\frac{m}{s}i} x_j \quad (4)$$

where s denotes the number of the segment.

2. Discretization of the time series is based on predefined breakpoints corresponding to the RTS. Symbolic Aggregate Approximation (SAX) is used assigning linguistic values to the segments (Fig. 3b). The given time series is mapped to the string “iiiihebbbbb”. At the same time, the linguistic transformation of the trend can be carried out in the following categories based on the value of the slope: up, down, straight-up, straight-down, straight, giving the string “ss-dss-ddds-

dss. In the representation phase each segment w_i is represented by a pair of characters (v, t) : mean value, local trend.

$$T = \begin{bmatrix} x_1^1 & x_1^2 & x_1^m \\ x_2^1 & x_2^2 & x_2^m \\ \dots & \dots & \dots \\ x_n^1 & x_n^2 & x_n^m \end{bmatrix} \Rightarrow R = \begin{bmatrix} (v_1^1, t_1^1) & (v_2^1, t_2^1) & (v_n^1, t_n^1) \\ (v_1^2, t_1^2) & (v_2^2, t_2^2) & (v_n^2, t_n^2) \\ \dots & \dots & \dots \\ (v_1^s, t_1^s) & (v_2^s, t_2^s) & (v_n^s, t_n^s) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (5)$$

3. In the classification phase, clustering is used to assign a class label to each segment. The sequence of clusters represents a dynamic pattern of the failure conditions. A feature-vector of fixed length is created for each segment of the multivariate time series (Table 1):

$$F^k = \langle (v_1^k, t_1^k), (v_2^k, t_2^k), \dots, (v_n^k, t_n^k) \rangle \quad (6)$$

4. One of the following classification techniques is used to obtain the classification model: Naïve Bayes, Support Vector Machine, or K-Nearest Neighbor. Confusion matrix is generated to evaluate each classifier.

Table 1. The reference time series (segments) coding.

Segment	Variable 1		Variable 2		...	Variable n	
	value	trend	value	trend		value	trend
1	v_1^1	t_1^1	v_2^1	t_2^1	...	v_n^1	t_n^1
2	v_1^2	t_1^2	v_2^2	t_2^2	...	v_n^2	t_n^2
...
s	v_1^s	t_1^s	v_2^s	t_2^s	...	v_n^s	t_n^s

4 Experiments and results

The analysis of the proposed fault diagnosis method has been completed on a set of real-life scenarios based on the available oilfield data.

4.1 Experimental settings

The experimental dataset contained five wells producing with ESP (from Baker Hughes and Schlumberger companies¹). The datasets from 15 sensors (Section 3.1) with 30 min and one hour time steps has been used. **Table 2** illustrates the results of the descriptive statistical analysis of the original data from one of the

wells after pre-processing. As it can be seen (gray shaded cell), original data had 89% of PTR missing values for that well along with acceptable (about 4%) number of missing values for current and voltage. For imputation and elimination of spikes, multivariable imputation with PCA, Kalman filter, and Hampel method were used. During the imputation, even PTR values were successfully estimated. After that, the data were standardized. **Fig. 4** illustrates the pre-processing results.

Table 2.

Descriptive statistical analysis of the original data.

	PIP	PDP	TIP	TM	CLA	VIB	FRE	IA	IB	IC	Vout	PTP	PB	TB	PTR
Nobs	3228	3228	3228	3228	3228	3228	3228	3228	3228	3228	3228	3228	3228	3228	3228
NAs	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Min	1230	839	122	125	11.8	0.03	56.4	47.5	49.5	46.0	3735	9.40	9.90	26.70	65.5
Max	1402	3291	127	154	11.9	0.40	60.6	98.3	99.6	97.9	4143	13.8	12.4	112.6	68.6
Mean	1289	2994	126	126	11.9	0.23	57.4	88.6	90.1	88.1	3876	11.88	11.06	108.90	66.56
Median	1281	2998	126	125	11.9	0.20	57.0	90.7	92.1	90.2	3825	11.8	11.1	110.2	66.5
Variance	793	55018	0.37	4.41	0.00	0.01	0.59	42.5	42.0	44.8	12909	0.34	0.27	43.26	0.45
Stdev	28.1	234.5	0.60	2.10	0.01	0.07	0.77	6.52	6.49	6.70	113.6	0.58	0.52	6.58	0.67
Skewness	1.63	-7.70	-2.3	12.7	-1.77	-0.4	2.69	-2.58	-2.54	-2.59	1.46	0.44	0.31	-9.42	0.45
Kurtosis	2.05	64.50	17.7	168	16.1	-0.34	6.63	10.0	9.69	10.0	0.42	-0.12	-0.36	103.7	-0.75
Original Miss, %	0.53	0.53	0.53	0.53	0.53	0.68	2.04	3.75	3.75	3.75	3.75	2.11	2.04	2.01	89.6

Fig. 4. Pre-processing results (massing values' imputation and despiking) of the PTP variable: black line – original TS, blue line – TS after pre-processing.

Different combinations of variables (based on feature selection, correlation analysis and expert opinion) were studied. Correlation analysis showed different results for different wells, so experiments included 15 (all) sensor variables, 7 (expert choice) and 9 (correlation analysis) variables. 1-week, 2-weeks (360 points in the case of the 1-hour scale and 720 points for 30 min.) and one-month windows were used for the segmentation. Each reference time series was characterized by two parameters: trend and level. To describe the level, two techniques were applied: the mean and the SAX with the alphabet of 10 symbols.

Due to the space limits, we describe the results for several most typical scenarios (**Table 3**). The following classifiers were used: kNN, Naïve Bayes, n-hidden layers ANN (numerical variables), and Random Forest (categorical variables). The ratio 75-25 was selected for

training and testing sets. It should be mentioned that ANN implement regression, so the predicted variable was rounded to the nearest integer. To measure classification accuracy, success rate (quotient between correct predictions and total predictions) $R_s = N_a/N$ was used, where N is the number of observations, M - number of classes, N_a is the number of hits, s. t.:

$$N_a = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta(c^i, c_M^i) \quad (7)$$

4.2 Experimental results and discussion

In **Tables 3 and 4**, the experimental results summarize clustering and classification results. Classification data are obtained from confusion matrixes for testing dataset. **Fig. 5** shows the results of determining the number of clusters and **Table 5** represents the results for the k-NN classifier for Scenario 7. The original size of seven selected clusters for this scenario is: 63, 58,

¹ There are some differences in the measured parameter set and measurement conditions, which should be made homogeneous at the pre-processing stage.

91, 70, 43, 80, and 45 samples. The following best variables were obtained during feature selection with random forest algorithm: VOUT-mean, IC,-mean, PDP-mean, PTR-mean, PIP-mean, PTP-mean, TM-mean,

PB-mean, TB-mean, VIB-mean, TP-mean, and PDP-slope. These 12 variables were used for final classification (Table 4). For the rest of scenarios similar results were obtained.

Fig. 5. Determining of the number of clusters with no-hierarchical a) and hierarchical b) methods

Table 3.

Clustering results for Scenario 3.

PI sl	PI sax	PD sle	PD sax	TI sl	TI sax	CLA sl	CLA sax	IB sle	IB sax	PTP sl	PTP sax	PB sl	PB sax	TB sl	TB sax	Cluster
s	g	s	i	s	g	s	i	s	h	s	i	s	h	us	h	4
s	g	s	i	s	h	s	h	s	h	s	i	s	h	s	i	3
s	g	s	i	s	h	s	h	s	h	s	i	s	h	s	i	3
s	g	s	i	s	h	s	g	s	i	s	i	s	h	s	i	3
us	g	d	h	s	h	s	h	ds	i	d	h	s	h	s	i	3
s	g	ds	e	s	h	s	h	ds	h	ds	e	s	g	s	i	3
s	g	s	b	s	h	s	h	s	g	s	b	s	g	s	i	5
s	g	s	b	s	h	s	g	s	g	s	b	s	h	s	i	5
s	g	s	b	s	h	s	g	s	g	s	b	s	h	s	i	5
s	g	s	b	s	g	s	g	s	g	s	b	s	h	s	i	5

Table 4.

Classification results.

Scenario	Sensors/ Vars	Clusters	Type	RTS, weeks	k-NN	Naive Bayes	ANN-1 /ANN-2	RF
Sc1	15/30	8	N	2	94	91	89	
Sc2	9/18	6	N	2	96	88	92/84	
Sc3	9/18	6	C	2				92
Sc4	7/14	6	N	2	93	88	86	
Sc5	7/14	6	C	2				89
Sc6	9/5	6	N	4	96	85	82	
Sc7	11/11	7	N	1	97	92	90	

Table 5.

k-NN confusion matrix for Scenario 7 testing data, mishits are shadowed.

Cluster	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1	14	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	0	15	0	0	0	0	0
3	1	0	21	0	0	0	0
4	0	0	0	19	0	0	0
5	0	0	0	0	9	0	0
6	1	0	1	0	0	20	0
7	0	0	0	0	0	0	10

During the experiments, dynamic patterns (a sequence of clusters) characterizing scale failure conditions was obtained. For sc7 the pattern corresponding to the reference window from Fig. 1 is “333355” (Table 3). In all experiments, the mean or linguistic label dominated the trends, so the slopes can be excluded (see sc7). Nearest neighbor method (k-NN) outperformed other classifiers in all experiments while neural networks register relatively poor performance in classifications. The use of numerical variables gives better

accuracy compared to categorical variables. The number of clusters and importance of variables varied between experiments. The accuracy of the classifications depends considerably on the number of segments and number of clusters. In general, the methodology allows generating precise classifications reaching values of 93-97% of hits with k-NN.

The algorithm has been programmed in R, using the following main libraries: fBasics, missMDA, randomForest, caret, imputeTS, TSrepr, TSclust, mclust, klaR, class, e1071, mlr, MASS, and RSNNS.

5 Conclusions

In the paper, the MTS pattern recognition method based on reference windows and used for the detection of fault patterns of electric submersible pumps caused by scales is described. The main contributions of this paper are:

- a. We use a large amount of unlabeled data to describe patterns to build the model, so the fault can be effectively detected and classified correctly.
- b. Due to the use of the sliding window and different from the current process monitoring methods that detect and diagnose the fault in a different time, our method can simultaneously get the results of detection of fault conditions and diagnosis in a monitoring process at different stages of the fault progress. Moreover, while the time advance, the diagnosis is further confirmed or discarded as more windows are involved in the classification process.

In the future work, a memory-based (remembering the previous segment) classifier can be generated to identify the sequence of clusters.

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